

EVIDENCE-BASED
TOXICOLOGY

Evaluation Report (Round 02) for **TEBT-2025-0002**

Submission information table

Submission Title	Pre-study on The Venom Toxicity of Vipera berus in Southeast Europe to Provide Foundations and Guidelines for Further Evidence-based Research on Venom Variability Throughout Eurasia
Submission Reference	TEBT-2025-0002
Handling Editor	Paul Whaley ORCID 0000-0003-4021-0785
Number of Reviewers	1 (editorial review)
Submission Type	Research Article ▾
Preprint DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14795382
Evaluation Stage	Editorial Review ▾
Evaluation Round	Round 2 ▾
Evaluation Date	21 Apr 2025
Recommendation	Revise ▾

Summary of article and editor recommendations

Note about triage evaluations: This triage evaluation report is not intended to be an exhaustive critique of a submission's methods, nor to supplant the peer-review process. The purpose of triage is to identify issues which need

to be addressed to ensure peer-review is a valuable process for both the manuscript authors and the peer-reviewers themselves.

This manuscript presents a scoping review of evidence for variation in the composition of *vipera berus* venom. The manuscript is significantly improved in structure and readability of the introduction and objectives. However, there are still issues that need to be addressed in order for peer-review to be likely to be worthwhile. Some of these issues remain from the previous round of evaluation. Some of the issues have become clearer now that the manuscript has been improved - which may be frustrating for the author, but does indicate solid progress.

Scoping reviews of the type described in the manuscript are rarely single-author undertakings. This may be one of the challenges with the research being described in this manuscript. The author may therefore wish to seek additional collaborators. Overall, I recommend significant revisions to clarify objectives, search, and some other aspects of the methods, a clearer presentation of the collected data and analyses that constitute the results of the scoping review, and a clearer boundary between results and discussion.

Checklist of minimum required information

P = Provided | R = Revisions recommended | X = Not Applicable

#	Status	Item checked
1	P	Preprint, relevant revision materials, and supplemental material available on Zenodo
2	P	Full name, affiliations, and ORCIDs (if available) of each author are present
3	X	Correct institutional co-authorship and disclaimer if official publication of EBTC
4	R	Structured abstract has been provided
5	P	Author contributions in the form of a CRediT statement have been given
6	P	Complete funding details are given, or “no funding” is declared
7	P	Informative disclosure of interests for all authors has been provided or disclosure declined
8	X	3rd-party data and program code are fully cited, if relevant (TOP 1, level 3)
9	X	Data and code availability has been stated and links to both are functional
10	R	One or more appropriate reporting checklists for submission type have been completed
11	P	Supplemental materials have plain English file names

Comments about minimum required information

1. A complete reporting checklist is still recommended (item #10 above). Scoping reviews are a relatively standardised study format. There are some inconsistencies and omissions in structure of the manuscript and presentation of data that suggest deliberate use of a reporting checklist would still be of benefit. The PRISMA extension for scoping reviews may be helpful ([PubMed](#), [docx download from Equator](#)). This would include guidance on e.g. reporting which studies were excluded, and other issues that have been identified with the manuscript.

Structured evaluation

KEY: R = Revisions recommended. N = No issues identified at this time. X = Not applicable.

Domain	D1. Clarity of objective and appropriateness of scoping review method
Compliance	Important issues identified ▾ that should be addressed prior to peer-review ▾
Specific Issues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> N ▾ Context and contribution, including motivation and position in field N ▾ Research mode appropriately confirmatory rather than exploratory R ▾ Target questions or knowledge goals clear and suitably focused X ▾ Other issues (indicated below)
Comments	<p>1. The background and objectives of the review have been significantly improved.</p> <p>2. Minor point, but the goal of the study, to summarise existing knowledge of “the venom toxicity of <i>V. berus</i> in Southeast Europe, focusing on Bosnia and Bulgaria” is stated at the beginning of the methods section. As the objective, this should come immediately after the introduction, or be the final paragraph of the introduction.</p> <p>3. Minor point, Table 1 shows the eligibility criteria for the review, defining what evidence is considered informative given its goals. It should be in the methods section. Note that the table does not match the criteria specified in section 2.2. The table should be a summary of the section.</p> <p>3. PECO statements are typically intended for comparative effect size studies, so are not necessarily the optimal structure for reviews with objectives such as this one. I suspect that SPIDER (Cooke et al. 2013), summary e.g. here will be more useful, even though it was originally intended for qualitative research.</p> <p>SPIDER would give something like (S) <i>V. berus</i> venom, in Bosnia and Bulgaria (PI) variability in toxicity and composition, (D) whatever study designs give insight into this, (E) whatever measures for P are appropriate, and (R) is probably not relevant.</p>

Domain	D2. Study selection methods have not excluded relevant evidence
Compliance	Important issues identified - that should be addressed prior to peer-review -
Specific Issues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> R - Appropriateness of eligibility criteria in context of research objectives R - Potential ambiguity or vagueness of the eligibility criteria R - Potential for screening process to exclude relevant evidence X - Other issues (indicated below)
Comments	<p>1. In relation to the eligibility criteria in general, I am not sure if they account for all the evidence that would seem to be informative of the review objectives.</p> <p>2. In particular, in relation to study design, it seems that the study designs that should be included might be quite broad, including case reports, studies, etc. and potentially even reviews (if they are informative of what has been studied). be included? It seems so, given the broad objective. Direct analysis of v berus venom would also seem to be relevant.</p> <p>3. The eligibility criteria outlined in section 2.2 are quite broad. This is OK, but it makes the judgements of eligibility more subjective. This presents a challenge at the screening step as to what the author considers to count as being this or that type of eligible or ineligible study. There at least needs to be a record of which studies have been excluded, for what reason, and a screening process that involves two investigators. These are the sorts of requirements that are made explicit in the reporting checklist the author has been recommended to use.</p> <p>4. Unfortunately, the exclusion of studies that are not open access is a serious limitation in the methods (and yet another demonstration of the need for research to be freely available at point of use - not that this helps us here). I would suggest asking for assistance with securing literature within EBTC. Many members have comprehensive library access and would be only too willing to support this work.</p>

Domain	D3. Search strategy is sufficiently transparent and comprehensive
Compliance	Important issues identified - that should be addressed prior to peer-review -
Specific Issues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> R - Search sensitivity, with adequate conceptual and database coverage R - Reproducibility of search strategy R - Validation of search strategy X - Other issues (indicated below)
Comments	<p>1. The PubMed search the authors provided yielded zero results when I tried it. Looking at the string, the way the concepts are concatenated would likely yield no results, and the syntax needed to allow near-match items to be included is not present. I suggest consulting a search specialist to make sure the search is robust.</p> <p>2. For the previous version I recommended using PRISMA-S for reporting of search strategy. I really do think this would help - even for scoping reviews, it is important</p>

	for methods to be transparent and theoretically replicated by the reader.
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Domain	D4. Data abstraction and coding methods are fit for purpose
Compliance	Important issues identified - that should be addressed prior to peer-review -
Specific Issues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> R - Code book or abstraction sheets show coding strategy appropriate to objectives R - Quality controls on data abstraction and coding decisions (e.g. duplicate) R - Transparency and reproducibility of coding or abstraction strategy X - Other issues (indicated below)
Comments	1. A code book, example data abstraction sheets, and table of characteristics of included studies from which the results of the scoping review are derived still need to be provided. Currently, there is no way for the reader to connect the results and discussion to any of the data that has been collected.

Domain	D5. Critical appraisal of individual studies is fit for purpose
Compliance	Important issues identified - that should be addressed prior to peer-review -
Specific Issues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> R - Suitability of appraisal instrument according to FEAT* criteria R - Quality controls on appraisal (e.g. duplicate appraisal, conflict resolution) R - Other issue (indicated below) <p>* Focus, Extent, Application, Transparency (Frampton et al. 2022)</p>
Comments	<p>1. Risk of bias would normally be assessed at the individual study level and be informative for comparative effect estimates. Since such estimates are not being drawn, it is difficult to see the need for risk of bias assessment in the study.</p> <p>2. Neither the approach to assessing risk of bias nor data on risk of bias judgements at the per-study level have been provided. It is therefore not possible to see how the findings of section 4.1.5.1 have been derived.</p> <p>3. The discussion of biases is potentially useful but should be more directly connected to the evidence and implications for conduct of the planned research. Bearing in mind comment 1 above, however, it may be unnecessary to do this if a full risk of bias assessment is planned for the follow-up work.</p>

Domain	D6. Validity of approach to deriving findings from scoping exercise
Compliance	Important issues identified - that should be addressed prior to peer-review -
Specific	R - Sufficiently detailed analysis pipeline for establishing target relationships

Issues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> R - Appropriately developed secondary or exploratory analyses R - Validity of analysis pipeline, e.g. statistical or qualitative methods, subgroups, etc. X - Other issue (indicated below)
Comments	1. My comments from the previous evaluation still largely stand. The discussion is too similar to the results, and the results section is lacking data. There should be a clear results section where data about the included studies is presented and analysed, that is then interpreted into a discussion section that interprets the results in the context of the research objective. At the moment, the results are too subjective and open-ended, and not clearly connected to data.

Domain	D7. Discussion of limitations and recommendations
Compliance	Important issues identified - that should be addressed prior to peer-review -
Specific Issues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> R - Limitations of the scoping approach sufficiently articulated R - Recommendations appropriate to scoping exercise informing future research X - Other issue (indicated below)
Comments	1. As for D6, I am not sure that my comments from the previous evaluation have been addressed.

Notes and guidance for submitting authors

This is an editorial triage report for systematic review protocols. It has been derived from the [CREST_Triage](#) tool for editorial appraisal of systematic reviews (Whaley and Isalski, 2019). CREST_Triage was designed to help editors make consistent, transparent decisions about whether to advance a SR submission to peer review. For EBT, CREST_Triage has been adapted for checking compliance with EBT's open data standards.

Citations

Whaley, P. and Isalski, M. (2019) *CREST_Triage* [Browser-based]. Available at: <https://crest-tools.site/>.

Whaley, P. and Roth, N. (2022) 'CREST_triage: Appraisal tools for systematic reviews and systematic evidence maps'. Open Science Framework. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/U4J5M>.

Wolffe, T.A.M. *et al.* (2019) 'Systematic evidence maps as a novel tool to support evidence-based decision-making in chemicals policy and risk management', *Environment international*, 130, p. 104871. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2019.05.065>.

Wolffe, T.A.M. *et al.* (2020) 'A Survey of Systematic Evidence Mapping Practice and the Case for Knowledge Graphs in Environmental Health and Toxicology', *Toxicological sciences: an official journal of the Society of Toxicology*, 175(1), pp. 35–49. Available at:

<https://doi.org/10.1093/toxsci/kfaa025>.